

Analysis of Temporal and Spatial Variation of Extreme Temperatures in Myanmar from 1987-2019

NWET NWET YIN^{1*}, Prof.Lou Yunsheng¹

¹ Collage of Applied Meteorology, Nanjing University of Information Science and Technology, Nanjing, China

Accepted May 19,2021

Published May 22,2021

*Corresponding Author:

NWET NWET YIN,

nwetnwetyin123@gmail.com

[m](#)

DOI :<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4781307>

Pages: 162-179

Funding: None

Distributed under

Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):

NWET YIN, N., Prof. Lou

Yunsheng. (2021). Analysis of

Temporal and Spatial Variation

of Extreme Temperatures in

Myanmar from 1987-2019. *North*

American Academic Research,

4(5), 162-

179. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4781307>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The study characterizes the patterns of climate change across Myanmar, several extreme indices are calculated from station values daily maximum and minimum temperature data. The trend analyses are implemented on 12 annual extreme indices for Myanmar, using observations from 27 surface stations with high-quality data for the period 1987–2019. Climact2 software is used in this study to calculate the indices, and simple regression methods are employed for the trend analysis. For the study region, the annual mean maximum temperatures are increasing in the central and lower parts of Myanmar, while the northern and eastern hilly parts are experiencing a great decrease. Our finding has shown that increasing maximum temperature anomalies rate was as high as 0.35 °C per decade during 1987-2019. Moreover, it highlighted that the highest increasing range was estimated in 2010 with +0.9°C and in 2019 with +1°C. Subsequently the year of 2000, the maximum temperature anomalies significant increasing was occurred during the chosen time interval. Additionally, the results of the study were that the temperature extreme indices of warm days (TX90p) and warm nights (TN90p) have increased and the number of cool days (TX10p) and cool nights (TN10p) has decreased. The analyses of extreme temperature indices detected a significant increase in the widely held of the stations, which further indicates that the country of Myanmar has experienced a warming trend. Extreme indices for temperature are contributed and its impacts are increasing so monitoring and investigation is able to support and reduce risks.

Keywords: EXTREME INDICES, MYANMAR, TEMPERATURE, CLIMPACT2

Introduction

Global warning does not occur uniformly over time and space. Some counties are warm more than others, some less and some not much at all. Over the period from 1880 to 2012, the global surface mean temperature indicated a warming trend of 0.85°C (IPCC, 2013). The warming rate was 0.12 (0.08–0.14) °C/decade since 1951 (1951–2012). Across the Southeast Asia, mean surface temperature had risen to 0.14–0.20 °C/decade with increasing trends in number of hot days, warm nights, and decreasing in number of cold days and cold nights (IPCC, 2013). The fourth Assessment Report of IPCC also reported that the global mean annual temperature had increased to

0.74°C from 1906 to 2005, and the linear warming trend rate was 0.13°C/10a in recent 50 years (Shifeng & Zhang, 2013, Jing et al., 2013). The world's nine warmest years have all occurred since 2005, and the five warmest years have appeared since 2010. Due to severe weather conditions such as drought and heat waves around the world, global climate research focuses on conditions related to extreme temperatures. Researchers and meteorologists believe that it is important to check the overheating current and accurately predict heat transfer. This is because extreme temperature changes have a significant impact on living conditions and economic development. Extreme weather and climate events have a negative impact on ecosystems, economies, and communities in a variety of ways (Griggs & Noguera, 2002). Researcher studies of (Donat et al., 2013, Easterling, 1997) resulted that the trends showed toward warming due to increasing of maximum and minimum temperature with significant increase in warm night, and significant decrease in cold night. (Easterling, 1997), and also reported that mean surface air temperature increased in the many part of globe but the temperature slightly decreased in the Southeast Asia region. They also reported a significant increase in minimum temperature and a significant decrease in diurnal temperature (DTR).

Myanmar is also one of the most vulnerable countries in the ASEAN Region to various kinds of natural disasters due to extreme climate (Donat et al., 2013). (Kreft & Eckstein, 2020), Myanmar was the second most affected by the extreme weather events during 1996-2015. Moreover, Myanmar has experienced the increases in maximum temperature and the decreases in minimum temperature during the period 1981-2010. The new highest maximum temperature record was detected in 2010, with a rate of 40-45°C during both April and May in some stations. So 2010 was recorded as the hottest year based on the instrumental records (Aung et al., 2017). Myanmar recently experienced an increase in temperature, a rise in sea level and also increases in frequency and magnitude of extreme weather events (Kreft et al., 2016). The day time temperature has increased in all over the country station from Deltaic to North up to the Central Myanmar. The hottest area is the rain-shadow area of Central Myanmar. Myanmar also has experienced increasing warm days and warm nights and decreasing cool days and cool nights at most of the stations in Myanmar (Sein et al., 2018). Nowadays, extreme temperature events and climate related event, such as floods heavy rainfall, drought, and cyclones landslides, extreme temperature, heat waves, become frequently and seriously. Moreover, the observed change in temperature have great implications for foods production and natural eco-system, it causes loss of biodiversity freshwater supply, and hazard risks. More in-depth knowledge on the temperature extreme is invaluable for impact assessment of the climate change occurring in this region. This study analyzed changes in extreme temperature indices using daily maximum and minimum temperature during 1987 to 2019 for 27 stations in Myanmar.

Materials and methods

1. Study Area

The Republic of the Union of Myanmar is a country, situated in Southeast Asia. It is roughly located between 9° 32' and 28° 31' N latitude and 92°10' and 101° 11' E longitude. It is bounded on the North and Northeast

by China, on the West by India and Bangladesh, on the East by Thailand and Laos PDR and also surrounded by Bay of Bengal on the west and Andaman Sea on the South. The total area of Myanmar is 676,578 square kilometers and composed of (7) States and (7) Regions. There are about 60 rivers in Myanmar. Most of the rivers flow from north to south. The main rivers in Myanmar are Ayeyarwaddy, Chindwin, Sittaung and Thanlwin respectively. The coastline of Myanmar is about 1470 km along the continental shelf which has a shallow bathymetry at the Deltaic. Myanmar has several mountain ranges including Bago Yoma, Rakhine Yoma, Tanintharyi and Shan Hills. It has three agro-ecological zones and eight physiographic regions which are Coastal zone, Central dry zone and Hilly zone. Myanmar's coastal line can be divided into three major coastal regions which are Rakhine, Deltaic and Taninthayi coastal regions. The length of the Rakhine coast is about 740 kilometers, Deltaic is about 460 kilometers and thus Taninthayi coast is approximately 900 kilometers. The study area is divided into three zones (Hilly, Dry and Costal (deltaic areas) regions), with 12, 5, and 10 meteorological stations respectively. These areas have the different climatic characters based on annual temperature and locality, altitude and geographical conditions. The slope of elevation is the highest in the northern part of Myanmar and the deltaic area (southern part of Myanmar) is the lowest. The distribution of detail information of selected (27) meteorological observation stations over Myanmar is shown in Figure (1) and Table (1).

Figure 1 Location of the distribution of ecosystems in the study area Map

This is a period of continuous and rapidly rise of temperature in March and April. The highest day temperature of (100°F) or (37.8°C) and above occurs in Central and Lower Myanmar areas. However, during the Strong El-Nino event, some stations recorded new maximum temperatures during March, April and May especially 46.0 to 46.5 Degree Celsius in central area of Myanmar. From about the middle of December, the serenity of the weather in Northern Myanmar is broken at intervals by a series of disturbances which travel

Eastwards across Northern Myanmar. The number and character of these disturbances vary, however, on the average four to six disturbances may be expected in each of the months of January and February. The precipitation associated with them is small in amount, nevertheless it is very important for the winter crops of Northern Myanmar area. Some of the disturbances receive rain over the whole of the Northern Myanmar while others confine their activities to the extreme North.

Table 1 Detail information of selected meteorological stations

No.	Station	WMO Code	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation(m)
1	Putao	48001	27.2	97.25	409
2	Hkamti	48004	26	95.42	146
3	Myitkyina	48008	25.22	97.24	145
4	Homalin	48010	24.52	94.55	130
5	Bhamo	48019	24.16	97.33	111
6	Kalewa	48025	23.12	94.18	109
7	Falam	48031	22.55	93.41	1372
8	Lashio	48035	22.56	97.45	747
9	Monywa	48037	22.06	95.08	81
10	Mandalay	48042	21.59	96.06	74
11	Mindat	48045	21.59	93.57	1395
12	Meiktila	48053	20.5	95.5	214
13	Taunggyi	48057	20.47	97.03	1436
14	Kengtung	48060	21.18	99.37	827
15	Sittwe	48062	20.08	92.53	4
16	Magway	48063	20.46	94.56	60
17	Kuaukphyu	48071	19.25	93.33	5
18	Pyinmana	48074	19.43	96.13	101
19	Loikaw	48075	19.41	97.13	895
20	Bago	48093	17.2	96.3	15
21	Patheingyi	48094	16.46	94.46	9
22	Kabaaye	48097	16.46	96.1	20
23	Hpa-an	48099	16.45	97.4	9
24	Mawlamyine	48103	16.3	97.37	21
25	Dawei	48108	14.06	98.13	16
26	Myeik	48110	12.26	98.36	81
27	Kawthong	48112	9.58	98.35	46

2. Methodology

According to the study, the recorded climate sections of daily maximum and minimum temperature data were utilized and obtained from Department of Meteorology and Hydrology in Myanmar (DMH). To analyze the spatial and temporal temperature patterns over Myanmar, the daily data were applied for the period of (33) years (1987-2019) from (27) meteorological observation stations. For annual temperature analysis, twenty-seven Meteorological observation stations and the data quality was checked before analysis. Quality test was carried out for all variables, in particular maximum and minimum temperatures which were checked using an R-based software tool Rclimdex. Data homogeneity was assessed using RHtests tool (Montero-Martínez et al., 2018). The calculation of the climate change indices was performed with ClimPACT2 software (<https://github.com/ARCCS S-extremes/climpact2>) which was developed by the Expert Team on Sector-specific Climate Indices (ET-SCI).

The input data file for ClimPACT2 software has a several requirements:

- (1) ASCII text file
- (2) Columns as following sequences: Year, Month, Day, P, TX, TN (NOTE: P units = millimeters and Temperature units= degrees Celsius)
- (3) The format as described above must be space delimited (e.g. each element separated by one or more spaces).
- (4) For data records, missing data must be coded as -99.9; data records must be in calendar date order. (ClimPACT2 user's manual).

To calculate all of the ClimPACT2 indices time-series of daily minimum temperature (TN), daily maximum temperature (TX) and daily precipitation (PR) are required. Daily mean temperature (TM) was calculated from $TM = (TX + TN)/2$. Diurnal temperature range (DTR) was calculated from $DTR = TX - TN$. Many indices were calculated at both annual and monthly time scales. It is two tables of core and non-core ET-SCI indices (ClimPACT2 user's manual). Out of many indices, 12 indices for temperature were selected as applicability across climates and available data that better explain the climate behavior of Myanmar (Table.2). In this study, ClimPACT2 software package was used to evaluate the ET-SCI climate indices for extreme weather conditions on temperature from 1987 to 2019 provided from Department of Meteorology and Hydrology (DMH).

Table .2 Temperature extreme indices used in this study.

ID	Indices Name	Definitions	Units
TXx	Max Tmax	Maximum value of daily maximum temperature	°C
TXn	Min Tmax	Minimum value of daily maximum temperature	°C
TNx	Max Tmin	Maximum value of daily minimum temperature	°C
TNn	Min Tmin	Minimum value of daily minimum temperature	°C

TN10p	Cool nights	Percentage of day when TN<10th percentile	%
TX10p	Cool days	Percentage of day when TX<10th percentile	%
TN90p	Warm nights	Percentage of day when TN>90th percentile	%
TX90p	Warm days	Percentage of day when TX>90th percentile	%
DTR	Diurnal Temperature Range	Mean different between daily TX and daily TN	°C
TMm	Mean TM	Mean daily mean temperature	°C
TXm	Mean TX	Mean daily maximum temperature	°C
TNm	Mean TN	Mean daily minimum temperature	°C

Additionally, Geographical Information System (GIS) software was generated by the spatial distributions of annual maximum and minimum temperature with the Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW) by interpolation method. Anomaly of mean maximum and minimum temperature was estimated and utilized the average value of all stations for the period 1987–2019 and focused on temporal changes and the spatial distribution of these changes for the 12 parameters that described extreme temperature.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Spatial Analysis of annual temperature

Annual maximum and minimum temperature are analyzed in the present study and spatial changing of the maximum temperature are shown in figure (2a). Excepting the hilly parts of eastern Myanmar, the annual mean maximum temperature has been above 30 ° C according to the studied results. The eastern hilly and Northern parts have observed with 23.5° C to 28° C. The results appear to show that annual mean maximum temperatures are increasing to the central and lower parts of Myanmar, while the northern and eastern hilly parts are experiencing a great decrease amount.

Figure 2b illustrates spatial analysis of the annual mean minimum temperature during (1987-2019). Annual Mean Minimum Temperature have observed higher than 20°C in Myanmar and between 13.2°C to 18°C in Northern hilly regions and Eastern parts. During the study period, Myanmar experienced the lowest mean temperature which have found Eastern hilly and Northern area and increased in Central Dry Zone and Coastal and Deltaic in Figure (2b).

Figure 2(a, b) Spatial distribution of annual mean maximum and minimum Temperature over Myanmar during the period (1987-2019)

3.2 Maximum and minimum temperature anomaly

Figure (3) represents the annual maximum temperature anomalies during the period 1987-2019 in Myanmar. The trend of the mean maximum temperature anomalies has indicated an upward warming of 0.35°C per decade. The highest increasing range has found in 2010 and 2019, accounting for $+0.9^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $+1^{\circ}\text{C}$. Figure (3) also shows that the trend line observed in the lowest decreasing range in 1992 with -0.9°C while 2019s is hot respectively. The trend line in Figure (3) indicates that there were negative anomalies trends during 1987-2002, except in 1998s. The maximum anomalies trend with greater than 0.5°C has detected in 1998s, 2005s, 2009s, 2010s, 2012s, 2014s and 2019s. During the 33-study period, from the late 2008s, the highest maximum temperature anomalies happened starting of 2010s ($+0.9^{\circ}\text{C}$) and 2019s as a warm year ($+1^{\circ}\text{C}$) respectively, the lowest anomaly detected in 1992s (-0.9°C).

Figure (4) shows that the annual minimum temperature decadal anomalies are increasing trend in Myanmar during the study period in 1987-2019. The highest minimum temperature observed in 1998s with ($+0.4^{\circ}\text{C}$), while the same range was in 1997 and 2013 with ($+0.3^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the lowest anomalies range studied in 1989(-0.6°C), 1992(-0.6°C) and 1997(-0.5°C), respectively. From 1994, the trend started with the increasing period, thus, it was fluctuated greatly between positive and negative anomalies. Therefore, the minimum temperature anomalies have not significantly changed in the study period.

Figure 3; Annual maximum temperature anomaly in Myanmar during (1987-2019)

Figure 4; Annual minimum temperature anomaly in Myanmar during (1987-2019)

3.3 Temporal Trends of Temperature Extreme Indices

Figure (5) indicates that there have been long-term trends in extreme temperature indices from 1987 to 2019. The rate of increase for the maximum value of daily maximum (TXx), the minimum value of daily maximum temperature (TXn), and minimum value of daily minimum temperature (TNn) have increased at rates of 0.25, 0.26 and 0.20°C per decade, respectively in figure (5a, b, d). However, the maximum value of daily minimum temperature (TNx) have decreased slightly at the rate of -0.04°C per decade in figure (5c). The temperature extremes indices, TXx, TXn, and TNn have shown an increasing trend, except only indicate a slightly decreasing trend of TNx.

The average number of regional cool days (TX10p) decreased significantly, at rates of -3.92 days per decade and cool night (TN10p) has decreased -0.79 days per decade, respectively in figure (5e, g). On the other hand, the number of warm days (TX90p) and Warm nights (TN90p) showed increasing trends with rates of

6.71 and 2.22 days per decade in figure (5f, h). In this study area, the number of cool days and warm days changed more obviously than the number of cool nights and warm nights. Both the mean number of cool days and cool nights have decreased since the end of 1993s in figure (5e, g), except for the number of cool nights (TN10p) in 1997. The number of cool days appeared in 1992, with the maximum value of about 42 days was observed in figure (5e). The decreasing number of cool days was faster than the decreasing number of cool nights. The number of warm days (TX90p) has increasing trends, with the maximum value of about 41 days which was detected in the 2010s by figure (5f). During the study period, the number of warm nights (TN90p) had increased slightly trends in figure (5h).

During the study period 1987-2019, the diurnal temperature range (DTR) showed significant increasing trends in the region with the range 0.24°C per decade in figure (5i). Annual temperature extremes indices of mean daily mean temperature (TMm), mean daily maximum temperature (TXm), and mean daily minimum temperature (TNm) also showed increasing trends, at rates of 0.2, 0.3 and 0.1°C per decade, respectively in figure (5j, k, l). Diurnal range temperature (DTR) has reached the peak of 11.7°C in 2010 and also followed in 2019 with 11.6°C in figure (5i). Therefore, the four indices of DTR, TMm, TXm, and TNm have shown significantly upward trends which relative to each other, was observed in figure (5i, j, k, l).

Figure 5; Long term annual trends of temperature extreme indices over Myanmar (a) TXx;(b) TXn;(c) TNx; (d) TNn; (e)Cool days (TX10p); (f) Warm days (TX90p); (g) cool night (TN10p); (h) warm night (TN90p); (i) DTR; (j)Tm; (k)TXm and (l) TNm during 1987-2019.

3.4 Spatial trend analysis of temperature extreme indices

During the decades, climate change causes impacts on natural disasters all over the world. Myanmar, a tropical country in Asia, air temperature is rising steadily, and this warming could lead to a warmer climate. Annual maximum and minimum temperature are analyzed in this study. Spatial distribution trend of the temperature extreme indices is shown in figure (6) and Table 3. Increasing trends are shown as the green symbols, decreasing trends are illustrated as white symbols. The stations are pointed with the yellow color background which represents significance at 5% level.

The spatial distribution of the temperature extreme indices of TXx, TXn, and TNn showed similar trends in fig (6a, b, d). For TXx, almost all stations showed an increasing trend, with 26% of the stations showing statistically significant trends ($P < 0.05$). Similarly, the TXn index increased by 77% of stations, the trend was significant with 11% of them (Fig6b). However, 18% of the station showed a negative trend, with Myeik station decreased significantly at a rate -0.26°C per decade which was shown in table (3). For TNx, 52% of the stations indicated increasing trends and 48% of the station studied negative trends in figure (6c). Table (3) shows that Mindat, Hpa-an, and Sittwe stations decreased significantly, at rate -0.77 , -0.55 , and -0.46°C per decade, respectively. For TNn, 70% of the station in the study area showed increasing trends, with 29% of stations increasing significantly in the central and eastern parts of the study area showed increasing trends in TNn, figure (6d). On the other hand, three stations showed the opposite trend in the northern part, with a significant decreasing on Putao station and five stations on coastal area also found a decreasing trend, with Sittwe station decreased significantly at rate -0.88°C per decade of the study area in Table (3), respectively.

The percentile-based indices for the number of cool days (TX10p) and cool nights (TN10p) were decreased trend of the study period (1897-2019). For the number of cool days TX10p, all stations showed a decreasing trend and the trend was significant ($p < 0.05$) for 59% of the station's which are shown in Figure (6e). There was a statistically significantly decrease by most of the stations in the southern part of Myanmar. A significantly decreasing trend in the number of cool nights TN10p was observed at the eastern part and central region, with the decreasing range from -6.71 to -3 days per decade and also western part of the station (Falam) had decreased significantly at a rate -1.93 days per decade in Table (3). Figure (6f, h) shows that warm days (TX90p) and warm nights (TN90p) have increased significantly in the study area. For warm days (TX90p), all stations showed an increasing trends, with 78% of the stations were found significant increasing trends in figure (6f). For the warm night (TN90p), 70% of the stations showed warming up trends with half of them were statistically significant increased, but two stations of the coastal area were observed significant decreasing trends in Figure (6h). Stations that is located the central and southern parts of Myanmar mainly observed an increase in warm days significantly in Figure(6f). Figure (6h) shows a significant increase in warm night, mostly in central, northwestern and eastern Myanmar.

Figure (6i) illustrates the diurnal temperature range (DTR), 66% of stations showed the positive trends with an increased significant trend of the coastal, northern and western parts of station. The diurnal temperature range of the two stations (Lashio and Bago) decreased significant with the rate -0.35 and -0.52°C per decade in

Table (3), respectively. Stations that located in the central and northern parts of Myanmar were not significant decreased in Figure (6i). For the mean daily mean temperature (TMm), the whole country of the study area displayed increasing trend, with 62% of stations observed significant increase in Figure (6j). For TXm and TNm, over all the station were increased trend in Figure(6k,l).Mean daily mean maximum temperature (TXm) illustrated an increasing significant trends in the central, northern, western and coastal part of Myanmar in Figure(6k). Figure (6l) shows that the mean daily mean minimum temperature of the stations in central Myanmar has risen significantly increased, the two stations of eastern part and the three stations of southern part were observed also statistically significant increasing trends.

Figure 6; Spatial distribution of trends in extreme temperature indices (per decade) from 1987-2019 over Myanmar; (a) Max: Tmax(TXx) (b)Min: Tmax (TXn); (c)Max: Tmin (TNx); (d) Min: Tmin(TNn); (e)Cool days(TX10p); (f) Warm days (TX90p); (g) Cool nights (TN10p); (h) Warm nights (TN90p); (i) DTR; (j)Mean (TMm); (k)Mean Tmax(TXm) and (i) Mean Tmin (TNm). Increasing trends are shown as the green symbols, decreasing trends as white symbols. The station points with the background of yellow color represent significance at 5% level

Table 3 Temperature trends for various ET-SCT indices Over Myanmar

Station	TXx (°C)	TXn (°C)	TNx (°C)	TNn (°C)	TX10p (days)	TN10p (days)	TX90p (days)	TN90p (days)	DTR (°C)	TMm (°C)	TXm (°C)	TNm (°C)
Myitkyina	0.029	0.022	0.003	0.033*	-0.19*	0.121	0.342*	-0.085	0.047*	0.017*	0.041*	-0.006
Bhamo	0.04	0.055	0.043*	0.07*	-0.259*	-0.664*	0.564*	0.578*	-0.004	0.058*	0.056*	0.06*
Putao	0.027	0.043*	-0.012	-0.042*	-0.279*	0.233*	0.253*	-0.222	0.065*	0.014	0.045*	-0.019
Mindat	0.018	0.071	-0.077*	-0.043	-0.373*	0.468	0.224	-0.193	0.09*	-0.003	0.042*	-0.048
Falam	0.021	0.058	0.015	0.038*	-0.194*	-0.193*	0.261*	0.341*	0.019*	0.034*	0.043*	0.025*
Hkamti	0.014	0.046	0.007	-0.002	-0.062	0.345	0.273*	0.223*	0.044*	0.011	0.033	-0.009
Homalin	-0.027	0.002	-0.009	0.083*	-0.093	-0.076	0.182	0.313*	-0.014	0.022	0.017	0.029
Kalewa	0.041	0.091*	-0.034	0.021	-0.279*	0.28	0.42*	0.04	0.062*	0.02*	0.05*	-0.011
Monywa	-0.004	0.013	0.011	0.047	-0.173*	-0.32	0.389*	0.168	0.007	0.03*	0.034*	0.027
Pyinmana	0.031	0.021	0.011	0.034	-0.123	-0.1	0.298*	0.161	0.009	0.024*	0.028*	0.02
Mandalay	-0.013	0.012	-0.006	0.07*	-0.12	-0.232*	0.284*	0.284*	-0.007	0.026*	0.022*	0.03*
Meiktila	0.022	-0.018	0.029	0.007	-0.102	-0.391*	0.16	0.166	-0.003	0.018*	0.016	0.02*

Lashio	-0.002	0.026	0.032	0.113*	-0.13	-0.482*	0.288*	0.366*	-0.035*	0.041*	0.023*	0.058*
Taunggyi	0.005	0.042	0.03	0.051	-0.254*	-0.671*	0.376*	0.436*	-0.007	0.043*	0.039*	0.046*
Kengtung	0.011	0	-0.017	0.029	-0.099	-0.043	0.024	0.033	0.005	0.009	0.012	0.007
Bago	0.042*	-0.026	0.057*	0.081*	-0.116	-0.417	0.247*	0.822*	-0.052*	0.044*	0.018	0.069*
Dewei	0.045*	0.021	-0.028	-0.002	-0.269*	-0.022	0.449*	0.021	0.034*	0.024*	0.041*	0.007
Hpa-An	0.007	-0.013	-0.055*	-0.045	-0.315*	0.281	0.137	-0.34	0.049*	0.001	0.026*	-0.023
Kaba-Aye	0.025	0.041	-0.026	-0.035	-0.219*	0.306	0.199*	-0.312	0.056*	-0.003	0.025*	-0.031
Kawthon	0.091*	-0.052	-0.052	-0.034	-0.038	-0.038	0.675*	0.04	0.079	-0.001	0.039*	-0.041
Kyauk Phyu	0.041*	0.022	-0.015	0.004	-0.409*	0.015	0.552*	-0.236*	0.046*	0.013*	0.036*	-0.01
Loikaw	0.026	0.071	0.027	0.02	-0.177*	-0.063	0.404*	0.221	0.016	0.03*	0.039*	0.022*
Magway	0.014	0.023	0.016	0.105*	-0.095	-0.065	0.161	0.693*	-0.043	0.037*	0.016	0.059*
Mawlamyine	0.058*	0.007	0.016	0.001	-0.338*	-0.296	0.567*	0.211	0.022	0.035*	0.047*	0.024*
Meik	0.058*	-0.026*	0.016	0.022	-0.098	-0.262*	0.385*	0.376*	-0.007	0.027*	0.023*	0.03
Pathein	0.049*	0.005	-0.022	0.015	-0.255*	0.398	0.574	-0.181	0.074*	0.013	0.05*	-0.024
Sittwe	0.003	0.097*	-0.046*	-0.088*	-0.377*	0.776*	0.44	-0.45*	0.103*	-0.013	0.038*	-0.064*

Note:*presents significant at the 5% level

Conclusion

This study analyzed changeability in detected temperature extreme indices using daily maximum and minimum temperature during 1987-2019 for 27 stations in Myanmar. The key result can be abridged as follows:

- (1) Annual average maximum temperature anomalies have increased by 0.35°C,
- (2) The warmest year which exceed by +0.5°C was higher than normal, such as 1998, 2005, 2009, 2010, 2014 and 2019,
- (3) The maximum temperature rate of increase is higher than the minimum temperature,
- (4) The highest rate of maximum temperature was detected in the central dry zone and Coastal zone,
- (5) the number of warm days and warm night are more frequent than the number of cool days and cool nights, and
- (6) The highest rate of increased temperature extreme indices is observed in the central region associated to the other regions respectively.

Central and Costal regions throughout Myanmar should be more alert of extreme temperature effect. If the temperature continues to rise in Myanmar, there could be the prospect of more severe weather conditions such as heat waves, droughts, heavy rain, flooding, landslide, volcanic eruption, depletion of water resources, overheating and so on. This study expects that extreme indicators of temperature are frequently monitoring and investigation support to reduce the risk.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor, Prof. Lou Yunsheng for his supervision guidance, support, encouragement, discussion, and suggestion during my study. I express the special gratitude to Nanjing University of Information Science and Technology, for providing them with the necessary facilities to carry out the study. No words can express my thanks to Dr. Kyaw Moe Oo, the Director General of Department of Meteorology and Hydrology, for giving me the chance to join this program and supporting me with valuable advice. I am thankful to Mr. Kyaw Lwin Oo, the Director of my department, for his guidance, support and encouragement.

Competing interests. The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

References

- 1) Aung, L. L., Zin, E. E., Theingi, P., Elvera, N., Aung, P. P., Han, T. T., Oo, Y., & Skalid, R. G. (2017). Myanmar Climate Report. *Norwegian Meteorological Institute*, 9, 105.
- 2) Donat, M. G., Alexander, L. V., Yang, H., Durre, I., Vose, R., Dunn, R. J. H., Willett, K. M., Aguilar, E., Brunet, M., Caesar, J., Hewitson, B., Jack, C., Klein Tank, A. M. G., Kruger, A. C., Marengo, J., Peterson, T. C., Renom, M., Oria Rojas, C., Rusticucci, M., ... Kitching, S. (2013). Updated analyses of temperature and precipitation extreme indices since the beginning of the twentieth century: The HadEX2 dataset. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 118(5), 2098–2118. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrd.50150>
- 3) Easterling, D. R. (1997). Maximum and Minimum Temperature Trends for the Globe. *Science*, 277(5324), 364–367. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.277.5324.364>
- 4) Griggs, D. J., & Noguer, M. (2002). Climate change 2001: The scientific basis. Contribution of working group I to the third assessment report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change. *Weather*, 57(8), 267–269. <https://doi.org/10.1256/004316502320517344>
- 5) IPCC. (2013). IPCC CLIMATE CHANGE 2013 Climate Change 2013. In *Researchgate.Net*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324>.
- 6) Kreft, S.; Eckstein, D.; Melchior, I. Global Climate Risk Index 2017: Who Suffers Most from Extreme Weather Events? Weather-Related Loss Events in 2015 and 1996 to 2015; German watch e.V.: Bonn, Germany, 2016; ISBN 978-3-943704-49-5y
- 7) Kreft, S., & Eckstein, D. (2020). Global climate risk index 2014. Who suffers most from extreme weather events? In *Think Tank & Research*.
- 8) Montero-Martínez, M. J., Santana-Sepúlveda, J. S., Pérez-Ortiz, N. I., Pita-Díaz, Ó., & Castillo-Liñan, S. (2018). Comparing climate change indices between a northern (arid) and a southern (humid) basin in Mexico during the last decades. *Advances in Science and Research*, 15(2014), 231–237. <https://doi.org/10.5194/asr-15-231-2018>

- 9) Sein, K. K., Chidthaisong, A., & Oo, and K. L. (2018). Observed Trends and Changes in Temperature and Precipitation Extreme Indices over Myanmar. *Atmosphere*, 9(12), 477. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos9120477>
- 10) Shifeng, Z., & Zhang, Y. (2013). *Temporal and spatial changes of temperature and precipitation in Hexi Corridor during 1955 – 2011. August.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11442-013-1035-5>

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

